

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

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Software and accompanying report on easy-to-understand maps of potential shaking (OEF, EEW and RRE)

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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
DSS	Decision Support System
EEW	Earthquake Early Warning
EEWD	Earthquake Early Warning Display
EMS-98	European Macroseismic Scale 1998. Grünthal, G. (1998). European Seismological Commission (ESC)
FWCR	F orecasting – E arly W arning – C onsequence Prediction– R esponse
GMPE	Ground Motion Prediction Equation
OEF	Operational Earthquake Forecasting
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration
POI	Point of interest
RRE	Rapid Response to Earthquakes
Shake map	Near-real-time map of ground motion and shaking intensity following significant earthquakes.

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1 INTRODUCTION

One of the items on the **TURNkey FWCR (Forecasting – Early Warning – Consequence Prediction–Response) platform** is easy-to-understand estimates of potential and actual earthquake shaking before, during and rapidly after the event for different groups of end-users. The different phases are referred to as OEF (Operational Earthquake Forecasting), EEW (Earthquake Early Warning) and RRE (Rapid Response to Earthquakes). Figure 1.1 shows a temporal overview of the different phases with respect to the earthquake origin time of a mainshock. EEW is relevant during the events of a mainshock or aftershock. RRE is relevant after a mainshock or after aftershocks. However, OEF is relevant in cases: prior to a mainshock as well as during an aftershock sequence.

Figure 1.1: Illustration of the chronological sequence of OEF (Operational Earthquake Forecasting), EEW (Earthquake Early Warning) and RRE (Rapid Response to Earthquakes). Source: TURNkey project proposal.

Within easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking, a particular focus is on presenting the uncertainties associated with these estimates in a form that the end-users can easily grasp. This report first describes the context of this task in the TURNkey project (Chapter 2). The overview of the end-users and their needs are summarized in Chapter 3. Some examples of existing solutions are presented in Chapter 4. Chapters 3 and Section 4.1 are based on the outcomes of other work packages of TURNkey. The new ideas about easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking for the FWCR platform are described in Chapter 5. The Work Package 3 partners evaluation is included in Chapter 6. The results of the extra end-user consultation by Work Package 2 are included in Chapter 7. Conclusions are given in Chapter 8.

The implementation of the easy-to-understand estimates of shaking in the platform and software requirements are presented in a separate document (D3.13: Requirements for software for easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking for different phases of earthquake warning (OEF, EEW, RRE)).

2 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT TO THE TURNKEY PROJECT

Among the natural hazards, earthquakes lead to the highest number of fatalities and, after severe storms, cause the second highest annual economic losses. This is not only true worldwide, but also for the European continent. The overall objective of TURNkey is to contribute to earthquake risk reduction, by reducing future economic and social losses in Europe and mitigating the direct and indirect consequences of earthquakes. To this end, information from the stakeholders of six Testbeds (Figure 2.1) was gathered during the socio-economic impact analysis among the end-user groups (Work Package 1) and the validation and standardisation of the TURNkey procedure and monitoring at the Testbeds (Work Package 2). The results from these work packages, described in several reports (D1.1 to D1.5, D2.6 and D3.1), are used as a starting point for designing easy-to-understand estimates of shaking. These estimates could, e.g., be communicated in the form of maps, graphs, traffic lights or audio signals. Work-in-progress comes from the other tasks in Work Package 3 (Assessment of ground motions before, during and after an earthquake). These results are considered as much as possible during the development of the ground-motion communication.

Figure 2.1: Distribution of TURNkey's project consortium partners (white dots) and the locations of the six geographically- based TURNkey Testbeds (TB-1 to TB-6, ellipses), plotted on the SHARE European Seismic Hazard of Giardini *et al.* (2013).

3 OVERVIEW OF END-USERS AND THEIR NEEDS

The end-users for the FWCR platform are visualised in Figure 3.1. The end-user requirements are being assessed using Participatory Action Research in three rounds. The first round has been reported in TURNkey reports D1.2, D1.3 and D1.4. The end-users considered in TURNkey report D1.2 consist of citizens, emergency responders, critical infrastructure providers and business organisations. The needs and expectations of citizens, civil protection and first responders were reported in TURNkey report D1.3 and those of critical infrastructure providers and business organizations in TURNkey report D1.4. Based on these reports we have formulated user stories for the three phases of information (Table 3.1, Table 3.2 and Table 3.3) which are relevant for shaking estimates and their uncertainties.

The second round of end-user consultation was performed by Work Package 2 in parallel to task 3.5. The results of the second round are included in TURNkey report D2.6. The highlights are included in the current report, but these were not used during development of the easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking. In addition, it was decided to conduct an extra round of end-user questions following the results of the Work Package feedback (Chapter 6). The extra round consisted of a short questionnaire by email. The results of this are included in Chapter 7. The final end-user consultation, using the visualisations on the FWCR platform, will be performed after finalisation of this report.

Figure 3.1: End-users for the FWCR platform

Table 3.1: User stories for OEF

User stories for Operational Earthquake Forecasting
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want to get ground shaking data: by location, period and intensity, in order to consider it for my critical asset lists.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want to get the ground shaking forecasts with different levels of certainty.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want to know the impact on business systems of the forecasted ground shaking.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want to use information about ground shaking in Disaster Risk Reduction management and business continuity planning.

Table 3.2: User stories for EEW

User stories for Earthquake Early Warning
As a citizen I want to receive a first ground shaking alert.
As a citizen or first responder I want to receive a first ground shaking alert in order to cut down on time to process multiple data inputs.
As a business or critical infrastructure I want shaking information targeted at specific employee groups, such as employees working at height, in confined spaces and operating lifting equipment, to limit injuries.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want shaking information in order to set up an automated switch to fail-safe mode of critical assets controlling hazardous (e.g. toxic, explosive) substances to limit damage and injuries.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want shaking information in order to set up automated braking of high-speed assets (e.g. trains) to limit injuries and accidents.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want to know the reliability of the time ranges for the overall EEW in order to minimize direct damage and limit injuries.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want to know when the ground shaking has passed.

Table 3.3: User stories for RRE

User stories for Rapid Response to Earthquakes
As a first responder or civic protection I want to know the strength of ground shaking in order to safely perform rescue work.
As a first responder or civic protection I want to know the strength of ground shaking in order to be able to coordinate a response.
As a first responder or civic protection I want to be able to report back on the effects of the ground shaking.
As a business or critical infrastructure operator I want to know the strength of ground shaking in order to minimize direct damage and limit injuries.

Based on a second round of end-user consultation, the high-level proposition for the TURNkey platform is visualised in Figure 3.2 and the high-level end-user requirements for OEF, EEW, RRE chronology in Figure 3.3. Relevant information from these figures for ground shaking estimates comprises hazard maps in the long term (pre-OEF) phase. These can be links to existing hazard maps from seismic authorities or standardised maps provided by the TURNkey platform based on the available hazard maps from seismic authorities. In the pre-main event OEF phase, the end-users need to be alerted to a raised hazard level. In the EEW phase, in the ideal case source parameters can be estimated and a shake map can be generated to feed an alerting system. The emphasis will be on the alert, as there will be too little time for platform operators to digest underlying source and ground-motion information. In the RRE phase, the information for the end-users will be based on shake maps, highlighting zones in which pre-defined critical ground motions have been exceeded. In the OEF aftershock phase, a map is produced with daily probabilities that a certain threshold ground-motion level is exceeded. Also, the increase in daily hazard with respect to the background hazard, is communicated.

Long term

TURNkey will model data, run static seismic damage scenarios (deterministic OEF; precompute EEW-based hazard estimates) develop tools (e.g. seismic hazard models, distribution of ground motions, GIS based data sets, maps of seismic ground amplification effects) in order to facilitate:

- Long term disaster planning
- Establishing a baseline for community resilience
- Long term built asset management/regional planning.

X days before impact

In terms of OEF for the main event/foreshocks the goal is to provide end-users with information on time, location and size with actionable uncertainties (through FWCR or 3rd party system) e.g. using ETAS. TURNkey will explore/ quantify to what extent this is possible and actionable.

X seconds before impact

If circumstances allow it, TURNkey will issue advanced warning of ground shaking to end users (latitude, magnitude and intensity) through FWCR or 3rd party system. Multi-criteria decision making tools determine whether an alert is issued. Alerts can be integrated with end-user systems. They are optimized for their needs and understanding.

X hours / days after impact

TURNkey will rapidly generate maps and indicators - **which are updated every x minutes / hours** - showing

- Damage probabilities of damage (at the level of city districts or building blocks)
- Estimations of social losses (casualties, population in need of healthcare and/or shelter)
- Indicators of system performance (road accessibility, (air)port functionality, hospital availability, etc.)

This will be based on

- Shake-maps from WP3
- Structural health monitoring of specific structures
- Eye-witness accounts of damage

This will be compatible with existing local systems
Data access will be restricted to local end-users

Figure 3.2: High-level TURNkey proposition for the FWCR platform (Source: TURNkey reports 1.5 and 2.6).

Figure 3.3: High-level end-user requirements against OEF, EEW, RRE chronology (Source: TURNkey report D2.6).

4 EXAMPLES OF EXISTING SOLUTIONS

4.1 Information from TURNkey reports

The literature review about existing solutions (TURNkey report D1.1) can be summarised into a list of lessons learnt for OEF and EEW. These are presented in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Lessons learnt from the existing solutions for OEF and EEW (Source: TURNkey report D1.1)

Phase	Lesson
General	Education is key
OEF	Communication by authoritative source
OEF	Recommended to use a mean probability using a logic-tree approach rather than a probability range as they are better understood and lead to less misinterpretation
OEF	Frequent updates needed because of quickly evolving aftershock forecasts
EEW	There is a true need for EEW
EEW	Provide simple messages
EEW	Individualisation of warnings is required

TURNkey Report D3.1 (part 1) provides more in-depth recommendations for OEF, EEW and RRE. The recommendations for OEF and EEW are included in Table 4.2. No specific recommendations regarding RRE shake map visualizations are given in Report D3.1.

Table 4.2: Suggestions for the design of the TURNkey OEF and EEW systems (Source: TURNkey report D3.1 - part 1 and D2.6). The recommendations which are relevant for the easy-to-understand estimates of shaking are highlighted in bold.

Suggestions for OEF and EEW
Use a maximum of five warning levels
Use simple vocabulary to describe the warning levels
Use standard colours (e.g. green, yellow, orange and red) for the warning levels (although care should be taken so that the colours are distinguishable for colour-blind people). Note: This recommendation will be superseded by recent literature with recommendations about colour usage
Consider both impact and likelihood when defining the warning levels
Do not associate precise numbers to the impact or the likelihood, but use easier to understand general terms
Do not provide warnings for small geographical areas (e.g. a town) but for larger regions (e.g. counties)
Provide warnings for specific critical infrastructure assets, such as bridges and tunnels
Provide a short list of actions that the public is recommended to take at each level. This recommendation is targeted at risk, rather than hazard
Provide warnings up to a week before the potential event (for OEF). Note: this is not yet possible from a scientific or engineering point of view
A respected and approved public authority should issue the warnings
Consider having a category for “warning no longer in force”, once the seismic hazard has reduced to its background level
Use historical events to calibrate the warning levels and make sure that the highest warning level is triggered for the largest historical event

4.2 Early ideas for visualisations

During the kick-off meeting, several ideas about the easy-to-understand estimates were collected. Inspiration was found from other fields. An example is from UK weather forecasts, in which words are used to express probabilities (Figure 4.1a), e.g. “low chance” of precipitation. Some caution is necessary here, because people tend to interpret these words differently (Figure 4.1e). An example of visualisation of a percentage is given in Figure 4.1b, where the proportion of people suffering from adverse effects of medicine are shown as red dots. A measurement value in combination with a threshold value is shown in Figure 4.1d. This example comes from the Dutch Corona dashboard. The figure shows that the number of positively tested people (per 100,000 inhabitants) is 15 while the threshold value is 7. The last example comes from the food industry (Figure 4.1c), showing a nutrition label with a combination of text (low, medium, high) and colours (green, orange, red) to express different levels.

Figure 4.1 (page 8): Inspirational examples from other fields. a) UK weather forecast. b) Risks as percentiles for the side effects of medicine. e) Food label showing nutrition information. d) Corona dashboard (example from the Netherlands, <https://coronadashboard.government.nl/landelijk/positief-geteste-mensen>). e) Numerical interpretations (in percentages) for each phrase (from Willems et al, 2020).

d) **Average number of confirmed cases per 100,000 inhabitants per day.**

This figure shows how many people per 100,000 inhabitants were reported yesterday as testing positive for coronavirus (number of confirmed cases).

Value of Thursday, 12 August - Source: RIVM

4.3 Extra examples of current solutions

In addition to the TURNkey reports, several current solutions were presented for inspiration by the project partners. Several examples are included in Figures 4.2 to 4.4. The examples are a mix of seismic hazard (the estimate of shaking) and risk (which includes vulnerability and impacts). Displaying hazard in an easy-to-understand way is the aim of the current task, while the seismic risk is addressed in Work Package 4. In general, hazard information can be expressed in two ways: as the probability for a given ground-motion level to be exceeded in a certain time period at the selected location (e.g. the probability of exceeding 0.05 g in the coming 24 hours) or as ground-motion level for a given probability of exceedance, which is related to the return period (e.g. Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) map for a return period of 475 years).

Figure 4.2: Example of existing visualisations provided by project partners. Example SICURO+ from Italy, showing the seismic hazard on municipality level from (<https://www.sicuropiu.it/>). Top: shaking levels (Valore di Scuotimento). Bottom: percentage of unserviceable buildings (Edifici coinvolti, Inagibili).

The SICURO+ website (<https://www.sicuropiu.it/>, Figure 4.2) shows the seismic hazard in Italy on a municipality level. Citizens are informed that the information represents the estimate of possible negative effects of possible future earthquakes on buildings and people. As such, this is an example of very-long term OEF. There are different types of information shown on the maps, i.e. danger, vulnerability, exposure and risk. Each of these options have their own colour scale. Shaking values are displayed for “danger” (Figure 4.2, top), using a rainbow colour scale inspired by the European Macroseismic Scale (EMS-98). The information is shown on a grid, which either fills the map or shows as squares depending on the zoom level. All other representations are filled maps on all scales and use monochromatic colour scales (example in Figure 4.2, bottom): pinks for vulnerability, blues for exposure and reds for three types of risk (human losses, buildings involved or economic losses). In this way, the colour of the map is an indication of the type of data one is looking at. For all maps, there is an arrow on the colour scale to the right, showing the municipality level relative to the national average. In the example, both shaking levels (Figure 4.2, top) and the number of unserviceable buildings (Figure 4.2, bottom) show higher levels than the national average. The visual information is also explained in text below the figures. No information about uncertainty is provided in the maps nor in the arrow on the right panels.

Figure 4.3 presents an example of mapping the seasonal weather trend for France from MétéoFrance. The map on the left shows where it will be normal (northern Europe), where it will be warmer than normal (southern Europe) and where it will be much warmer than normal (Italy, Balkan, Greece, Turkey). The colour scale has hot colours (pale red, showing orange-red on the map) for warmer and cooler colours (blue-green) for cooler than normal. Normal is indicated by pale yellow, showing transparent on the map. The uncertainty is included as probabilities of cooler, normal or warmer scenarios which are indicated by the bar next to the overall result and accompanied by text. This type of representation of deviation from the normal trend could be interesting for the OEF mapping.

Figure 4.3: Example of existing visualisations (in low resolution) provided by project partners. Example of a map showing the seasonal weather trend for France from MétéoFrance. Left: for June-August 2020. Right: for March-May 2021. Bottom: zoom of legend showing probabilities of a scenario cooler than normal (blue-green), normal (pale yellow) and warmer than normal (pale red). Dashed lines for regions where none of the three scenarios are dominant.

Figure 4.4 is an example of displaying the impact level of earthquakes to the public. The visualisation was developed by BRGM and ICGC (Institut Cartogràfic i Geològic de Catalunya) in the POCRISC project (<https://pocrisc.eu/fr>). The POCRISC Interreg project ran from 2018 to 2021 in the French, Spanish and Andorran Pyrenees. The visualisation is a combination of colours, labels and text. Uncertainty is not included in this example. Other examples from the POCRISC project include shake maps (Figure 4.5). A shake map shows the macroseismic intensity using the standard rainbow colour scale. The POCRISC shake maps have a disclaimer stating that they are automatically produced in the minutes after an earthquake and are not yet checked. If the earthquake happens in an area prone to aftershocks, the map can be seen as an example of an OEF map. It can also be used in this form, or after the quality check, as input for RRE. No information about uncertainty is included in the map.

Figure 4.4: Example of existing visualisations provided by project partners. Example of a proposal for a public index for rapid assessment of the impact of earthquakes in Pyrenees (BRGM, POCRISC project).

Figure 4.5: Example of existing visualisations provided by project partners. Example of a shake map for the Pyrenees, from the POCRISC project (<https://pocrisc.eu/fr/page/shakemaps>).

Figure 4.6: Screenshots of the EEWD for a play-backed scenario event with Level 1 (top), Level 2 (middle) and Level 3 (bottom) maps.

Figure 4.6 is an example of displaying EEW information taken from the Earthquake Early Warning Display (EEWD, Cauzzi et al., 2016), a free and open-source software developed in the REAKT project to display EEW information. EEW maps evolve in time as new information arrives, i.e. they continuously change. Figure 4.6 reports three snapshots corresponding to three representative temporal instants: instant at which the first joint estimate of magnitude and location is available (Level 1), intermediate instant (Level 2) and instant at which the “final” joint estimate of magnitude and location is provided (Level 3). After the Level 3 temporal instant, the earthquake is no longer

processed. The maps shows a background geographic map, a predictive shaking scenario (macroseismic intensity in this case), the available seismic network stations (orange triangles), the earthquake point source location and associated uncertainty (red circle and pale red ellipse), the target site (red & white dot) with a shaded region corresponding to an estimate of the region where EEW cannot be expected to provide advanced warning of strong ground shaking, the predicted P and S wavefronts (yellow and red circles) emanating from the epicentre and a summary of the earthquake magnitude and distance from the target site, along with the expected severity of shaking and the time prior to strong shaking at the target.

Figure 4.7 shows another example of displaying EEW platforms, namely the EaRly warninG demO (ERGO) (Iervolino, 2011), developed by staff of the RISSC Lab to test and demonstrate the potential of EEW in the Campania region, Southern Italy. ERGO processes in real-time the accelerometric data provided by a sub-net (6 stations) of the Irpinia Seismic Network (ISNet). The sub-net is installed in the main building of the School of Engineering of the University of Naples Federico II, in Naples (Italy). This is the target site of a prototype EEW. ERGO is able to perform real-time seismic hazard analysis and eventually to issue an alarm in the case of potentially dangerous events occurring in the southern Apennines region. ERGO is composed of the following four panels (Figure 4.7):

- (1) *Real-time monitoring and event detection.* In this panel two types of data are given: (a) the real-time accelerometric signals of the stations, shown on a 2 min time window and (b) the portion of signal that, based on signal-to-noise ratio, determined the last trigger (i.e., event detection) of a specific station (on the left). Because local noise (e.g., traffic) may cause a trigger on a station, the system declares an event (magnitude larger than 3) only if at least three stations trigger within the same 2 s time interval.
- (2) *Estimation of earthquake parameters.* This panel activates when an event is declared. If this condition occurs, the magnitude and location are estimated in real time as a function of evolving information from the first panel, based on a set of EEW algorithms. Here the expected value of magnitude, as a function of time and the associated standard error, is given. Moreover, the panel also shows (on a map) the estimated epicenter (red circle), its geographical coordinates and the origin time together with the recording stations (rectangles).
- (3) *Lead-time and peak-shaking map.* This panel shows the lead-time associated with S waves for the propagating event in the whole region. As further information, on this panel the expected PGA on stiff soil is given on the same map. This panel activates only if an event is declared from panel 1 and its input information comes from panel 2.
- (4) *Real-time ground-motion estimation and alarm issuance decision.* This panel performs real-time ground-motion estimation for the site where the system is installed based on information on magnitude and distance from panel 2. In particular, it computes and shows a real-time evolving probability distribution for PGA at the site. Because a critical PGA value has been established (arbitrarily set equal to 0.01 g) the system is able to compute the chance that this PGA value is exceeded as a function of time. If such a chance exceeds 0.2 (i.e. 20%), the alarm is issued and a green light turns to red. This panel also gives, as summary information, the actual chance that the critical PGA value is exceeded along with the lead-time available and the false alarm probability.

Figure 4.7: ERGO EEW platform, adapted from Iervolino (2011).

Figure 4.7 refers to a real event detected and processed in real-time by ERGO on February 01, 2010. The system estimated the event as an M 3.6, with an epicentre about 130 km from the site. Because the event was low magnitude and large distance, the chance that the critical PGA would be exceeded was negligible and the alarm was, correctly, not issued.

It is worth mentioning that in EEW there is a trade-off between the available lead time (i.e., warning time) and the level of information based on which the alarm issuance is decided. Consequently, different lead times may be computed for a given target region, each corresponding to a different number of stations providing EEW information. For example, Iervolino et al. (2009) selected 4, 18 and 29 stations for the Campania region (Southern Italy), representing three levels of information about the source of the earthquake: poor, large and full, respectively. Results in the form of maps were computed considering all possible hypocentres randomly occurring in the volume below the EEW seismic network for the region, up to a 12 km depth. This exercise resulted in maps representing the minimum, maximum and average lead-time values for the region (Figure 4.8). Iervolino et al. (2019) found that 18 stations is the minimum level of information to stabilize EEW uncertainty in terms of ground-motion estimates (and resulting alert using ground-motion-based decisional rules). Therefore, the 18-station average lead-time map can be considered as the reference for the design of real-time risk reduction actions; some of which are superimposed in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: Design lead-time map for the Campania region (southern Italy), modified from Iervolino et al. (2019).

An example of visualising uncertainty is provided in TURNkey report D3.1 (part 2) for the RRE of Testbed 2 (Pyrenees, Area of Luchon). Shake maps were produced for M_w 6.0 scenarios. The results are presented as PGA values (Figure 4.9, left panel) and the corresponding uncertainty (Figure 4.9, right panel). It is clear that the uncertainty is small at and near the stations and that uncertainty increases at longer distances from the station. It is, however, hard to visualise the PGA ranges from these two maps in one's mind.

Figure 4.9: Presentation of shaking estimates for an M_w 6.0 scenario for Testbed 2 near Luchon, from TURNkey report D3.1 part2. The left panel shows the shake map, the right panel the corresponding uncertainties. Square dots indicate the seismic stations, and the star corresponds to the epicentre. In this case, 15 virtual stations corresponding to the largest towns have been added.

A pilot OEF system for Italy was initiated during the REAKT project and additional funding from Italian Civil Protection (Marzocchi et al. 2014). To our current best knowledge, no other European nation has a similar national OEF programme. The philosophy of the OEF-Italy system rests on three concepts: (a) it is fully transparent such that the results are reproducible by anyone; (b) the system is open to any modelers who want to contribute, provided the model is under test in at least one CSEP experiment; and finally (c) it minimizes scientific controversies because of the use of ensemble models based on objective statistical evaluation of the model's performance, significantly reducing the subjectivity that is implicit when choosing the model to be used. A detailed discussion can be found in Marzocchi et al. (2014).

Seismicity rates from the OEF-Italy system cover the whole national area and some coastal regions. The system uses an almost-real-time earthquake catalogue from recordings of the National Seismic Network (<http://iside.rm.ingv.it>), which are available and updated 20–30 minutes after each event. Two main outputs of the OEF-Italy are (Marzocchi et al. 2014): 1) the weekly earthquake forecast of different magnitudes (i.e., 4+, 5.5+) in which the system forecasts the probability that at least one earthquake with local magnitude of at least 4 or 5.5 will happen within the next week and 2) the weekly probability of ground shaking for modified Mercalli intensities (MMIs) VI, VII, and VIII. An example snapshot of the Italian OEF system is shown in Figure 4.10. The weekly earthquake forecasts and seismic hazard are updated every day or just after an earthquake with M3.5 (local magnitude) or larger.

Figure 4.10: An example snapshot from the Italian OEF dashboard (Marzocchi et al., 2014). The example shows the map with the current probabilities for intensities larger than VII. The timeline graph on the lower right shows the probability history for part of the northern Apennines (marked on the map of Italy). The upper right reports the probabilities of the last run of the system.

4.4 A different approach for hazard: ThinkHazard

World Bank's GFDRR's platform ThinkHazard ([Think Hazard](#)) provides an approach for different geophysical, hydrological and meteo-climatic hazards. The documentation can be found on [ThinkHazard! Documentation \(gfdrr.github.io\)](#). Earthquakes are one of the geophysical hazards considered. Of particular interest to the easy-to-understand maps of shaking is the alternative way to define hazard levels (Figure 4.11). Commonly, hazard is expressed as the hazard measure for a given level of probability of exceedance (Figure 4.11, left). For end-users, however, the definition the other way around (Figure 4.11, right) is probably more useful: defining a level of hazard in terms of the probability of a hazard measure (e.g. peak ground acceleration) exceeding a given threshold to cause damage. The intensity level for a type of hazard above which damage is expected to occur and the assessment of how frequently that intensity might be exceeded is relevant information. It helps users prioritize and manage multiple hazards with the greatest chance of causing damage to their interests, rather than identify the exact impact.

Figure 4.11: Comparison of Think Hazard frequency-based approach, and common intensity-based approach (from ThinkHazard! <https://gfdrr.github.io/thinkhazardmethods/>).

4.5 Maps and colours

An extensive study about what defines the success of maps and additional information on a multi-hazard platform, for which earthquakes is one of the hazards, is given by Dallo et al. (2020). They tested different start page designs and hazard announcements representing the diversity of elements used in multi-hazard platforms. Their main results are that the participants prefer a start page consisting of a single map with textual information about the current hazards below the map (Figure 4.12). The earthquake announcement consists of a combination of pictograms and textual instructions. The symbols on the bottom of the screen represent the need for a multi-channel communication strategy to inform as many people as possible. In addition, participants of the survey prefer hazard classifications with four or five hazard categories.

Figure 4.12: Participants' preferred start page design from Dallo et al. (2020).

The examples included so far all use colours to be informative of certain levels. If colours are chosen appropriately, they can be a useful means to transfer information. However, lots of bad choices can be made regarding colours, which then complicate rather than facilitate, the understanding of the information. A colour scale is often referred to as a colour map, but we refer to colour scale to avoid confusion with a geographical map on which colours of a chosen colour scale are plotted.

A recent paper by Crameri et al. (2020) includes useful recommendations for the scientific use of colour scales. They recommend against using the rainbow colour scale. Everything that can go wrong in a colour scale goes wrong for the rainbow colour scale: it cannot be properly seen by all types of colour-vision deficiency, it does not plot right on grey-scale, the intensity does not increase over the scale and the intervals between different colours are not evenly spaced over the values they represent. Some of these aspects are illustrated in Figure 4.13, which also includes suggestions for good choices of colour scales. Rainbow or jet, at the bottom, fails to reproduce a meaningful smooth gradient. The other colour scales in Figure 4.13 are all universally readable for colour-vision deficiency and when

printed in grayscale. There are various freely available "good" colour scales, such as viridis, magma, plasma and inferno from Matplotlib (Figure 4.14). Another example in Crameri et al. (2020) is "batlow" (see Figure 4.13), which is available from <http://www.fabiocrameri.ch/batlow.php>.

Figure 4.13: Colour vision tests from Crameri et al. (2020). The colour scales on the left are shown in the middle for various types of colour-vision deficiency and on the right for grey-scale.

Figure 4.14: Perceptually uniform sequential colour scales from Python Matplotlib.

Crameri et al. (2020) recommend the following for scientifically derived colour scales:

1. Colour scales should be perceptible for colour-vision deficiency and in grey-scale.
2. Colour scales should be perceptually uniform, meaning that the same data variation is weighted equally across the dataspace.
3. The perceptual colour order should be such that the colour gradient is easily and intuitively understandable and allows qualitative understanding of a data set. This means that both lightness and brightness should increase linearly. This is to easily discern and compare significant values and to avoid the perception of artificial gradients.
4. For divergent data centred about a central value, a divergent or a multi-sequential colour map should be chosen. This clearly and intuitively distinguishes either side of the axis.
5. An axis relating colours to data values should be provided.
6. The lightness of background has an influence on the colours displayed. The background creates contrast to the displayed data, both in lightness and colour.

In addition, Crameri et al. (2020) provide a flowchart for choosing the right scientific colour map (Figure 4.15). Ground motion shaking levels form a sequential dataset, which can be displayed continuous or discrete (top part of Figure 4.15). More intense colours are generally associated with more severe levels. Following the bottom part of Figure 4.15, a light background is recommended.

Although Crameri et al. (2020) recommend against using the rainbow colour scale, it is commonly used for displaying shaking levels as macroseismic intensities. Because of this common use, it will be hard to avoid. In our development, however, we will consider using an alternative scientific colour scale.

4.6 Take-away messages for the development of easy-to-understand estimates of shaking

In this chapter, earlier issued TURNkey reports were summarised and several examples were presented. The take-away messages are:

- Use of a limited number of levels (maximum of five).
- Use simple vocabulary.
- Do not associate precise numbers but use easier to understand general terms.
- Use of a proper scientific colour scale. However, the use of the rainbow for macroseismic intensity scale is so common that it probably cannot be avoided.
- Consider defining a level of hazard in terms of the probability of a hazard measure (e.g. peak ground acceleration) exceeding a given threshold to cause damage, instead of the commonly used hazard measure level for a given probability.
- Use a combination of a map with textual information and pictograms.

Figure 4.15: Flowchart for choosing the right colour map, from Cramereri et al. (2020). The nature of a given dataset should be matched by a suitable colour map class, type and colour combination.

5 THE NEW EASY-TO-UNDERSTAND ESTIMATES OF SHAKING INCLUDING UNCERTAINTY

5.1 Process of development

The easy-to-understand estimates of shaking were developed by KNMI with input from the project partners of Work Package 3. During the kick-off meeting of Task 3.5 first ideas were exchanged. In parallel, flowcharts for the different phases were coordinated by NORSAR. The easy-to-understand estimates of shaking are part of the flowcharts which are described in Section 5.2. The essential part of the visualisation consists of using a slider to display uncertainty (section 5.3). The products for the different end-users are described in section 5.4. The first rough sketches of the easy-to-understand estimates of shaking were presented during an online Work Package 3 meeting on 6 March 2021. Feedback on the first drafts was gathered during the meeting.

Following partners' suggestions, KNMI designed two types of visualisations (Section 5.5) and made several worked examples based on real Testbed data. These draft visualisations were presented to the Work Package 3 partners during an interactive online session on 6 May 2021. The results from the partner evaluation are described in Chapter 6 and the short end-user consultation in Chapter 7. The recommendations are used to define the “almost-final” visualisations, described in the separate Deliverable D3.13 (Requirements for software for easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking for different phases of earthquake warning (OEF, EEW, RRE)). D3.13 contains a description of the easy-to-understand estimates of shaking to be implemented on the FWCR platform. A final end-user consultation by Work Package 2 at the end of 2021 will result in the final definition of the easy-to-understand estimates of shaking on the FWCR platform.

5.2 Flowcharts for OEF, EEW and RRE

The easy-to-understand estimates of shaking form a part of the information and functionality of the FWCR platform. The segments related to shaking levels are visualised in the flowcharts of Figures 5.1 to 5.3 for OEF, EEW and RRE. These flowcharts may be further updated during the course of the project.

The concept of OEF is described in Figure 5.1. The black boxes mark static data (which might be updated outside of the OEF system using input data recorded in the Testbeds). Red boxes mark dynamic data employed in the OEF process. The forecasting module is initiated if the dynamic seismicity data (e.g., the new main shock-aftershock earthquake sequence) contains at least a certain number of events and allows a stable evaluation of the magnitude of completeness M_c . The Bayesian Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) procedure for updating the epidemic type aftershock sequence (ETAS) model parameters is carried out adaptively. Given the updated parameters, the ETAS seismicity model is used for the aftershock forecasting. The output daily seismicity rate is fed into the time-dependent probabilistic seismic hazard analysis (PSHA) module, while the background seismicity rate evaluated from the static data (e.g., seismic zonation) is used in the conventional PSHA module. Logic trees within the PSHA modules are included for magnitude, hypocentre depth, ground-motion prediction equations (GMPEs) and non-seismic data. The hazard curves (e.g., daily probability of exceeding a certain PGA threshold) from the PSHA modules are used to compute the probability gains. In the risk and loss module, the hazard curves, together with the static data regarding site amplification, exposure, and vulnerability, are used to compute the risk curves (e.g.,

probability of exceedance of damage, human and economic losses). Finally, the cost-benefit analysis is performed based on the loss reduction action cost models (e.g., decision criteria, proposed actions and their costs and reducible/non-reducible loss) as part of the Decision Support System.

Figure 5.2 illustrates the concept of the regional EEW system. Green and red boxes mark static and dynamic data, respectively. Currently, only seismological data from the sensor network are considered for EEW; potentially, data from smartphone accelerometers may be added at a later stage. The continuous data stream from the network is analysed automatically employing SeisComp to detect events. In case of event detection, the location and magnitude is sent to the TURNkey scientific engine. In case that the event is identified as being relevant, a quantitative estimate of ground shaking is computed, employing the magnitude-distance estimate and GMPEs retrieved from the library. The calculated ground shaking is then compared to a general testbed-specific threshold as well as thresholds determined for critical infrastructures within the earthquake alert message system. If the threshold is exceeded, an alarm is triggered and sent to the information dashboard on the user interface of the platform. The user interface will additionally contain a lead time plot as well as ground shaking maps updated at specific times (at the time of the first incoming estimate, after a certain portion of the time defined for updating earthquake parameters has passed and once a final estimate is available).

Figure 5.3 illustrates the concept of the RRE system. Once again, green and red boxes indicate static and dynamic data, respectively. For RRE, three sources of data are used: the continuous data flow from the seismometer network, intensities extracted from felt reports employing crowdsourced data via the LastQuake app and on-site observations from a potential strong-motion or onsite network. Using additional information (faulting mechanisms, site amplification and GMPEs extracted from the library), a quantitative estimate of shake maps and their uncertainties are computed employing a Bayesian algorithm that is more advanced than that used for ground shaking calculation in EEW. These shake maps are utilised in the loss assessment and stochastic damage scenario computations to estimate the damage distribution, casualties and injuries for residential buildings, the damage or functional state, respectively, for critical infrastructures and the accessibility for infrastructure systems, such as road networks in order to identify the most suitable routes for evacuation and rescue purposes. Both shake maps and estimated damages are sent to the information dashboard on the user interface.

Figure 5.1: Flowchart for OEF (updated based on the version sent on 7 January 2021 prepared by John Douglas and Alireza Azarbakht from the University of Strathclyde).

Fixed at first but potentially updated using inputs from testbeds, Tasks 3.5 + 5.3 + 6.4

t_1 : first incoming estimate
 t_2 : 20% of time span in which EQ parameters are refined
 t_3 : final estimate

Concept of regional EEW system
 In Task 3.3
 Outside Task 3.3

Figure 5.2: Flowchart for EEW (version: 16 June 2021)

Fixed at first but potentially updated using inputs from testbeds, Tasks 3.5 + 5.4 + 6.4 + WP4

Figure 5.3: Flowchart for RRE (version: 16 June 2021)

5.3 Displaying uncertainty using a slider

The basic idea of showing uncertainty is using a slider. Depending on the position of the slider, the corresponding map shows a low, a best or a high estimate of shaking. These levels are defined by the average estimate of shaking and the standard deviation of that estimate. For PGA, the average is usually calculated for the natural logarithm of PGA and hence σ_{PGA} is expressed in log units. The level of uncertainty can be chosen as one or two standard deviations. During the Work Package 3 meeting of 6 March 2021, there was consensus to use two levels around the best estimate. The average PGA is referred to as “best estimate of shaking” and the values plus or minus two standard deviations as “high” or “low” estimates, respectively. The definition in terms of PGA and macroseismic intensity is given in Table 5.1. The macroseismic intensity refers to the European Macroseismic Scale (EMS-98). In the remainder of the document, this is referred to as “intensity”. The standard deviation of intensity is defined on a linear scale.

Table 5.1: Definition of uncertainty for RRE maps

Words	Definition in terms of PGA	Definition in terms of macroseismic intensity
Low estimate of shaking	$\frac{\text{average PGA}}{e^{2\sigma_{PGA}}}$	<i>average macroseismic intensity</i> – 2σ
Best estimate of shaking	<i>average PGA</i>	<i>average macroseismic intensity</i>
High estimate of shaking	<i>average PGA</i> · $e^{2\sigma_{PGA}}$	<i>average macroseismic intensity</i> + 2σ

The values for PGA and macroseismic intensity, including their uncertainties, can be converted into the other using the equations given in Caprio et al. (2015). These equations are implemented in the FWCR platform by NORSAR.

The low, best and high estimates of shaking for the OEF maps are defined by the 2nd, 50th and 98th percentiles (corresponding to the median minus or plus two standard deviations). The values for the OEF maps are calculated by the TURNkey engine. These values will be used to produce the corresponding maps.

5.4 Products for different warning phases

The products within the task of easy-to understand estimates of potential shaking are listed in Table 5.2. This list is the result of several Work Package 3 meetings with input from project partners. The products are sorted per phase. A description of each product follows after the table.

Table 5.2: Summary of products for easy-to-understand shaking estimates

Phase	What?	How?	To who?
OEF	Hazard: Long-term (background) hazard and short-term hazard (for aftershocks)	Two maps with daily probability of a specified critical ground motion value. The background hazard is based on median hazard. The short-term hazard includes ranges of low, best and high estimates of shaking using a slider.	Business / Operators / Civic protection
OEF	Change in hazard: ratio between short-term and long-term hazard, probability gain (PG)	Map of probability gain for entire aftershock zone including ranges of low, best and high estimates of probability gain using a slider.	Business / Operators / Civic protection / First responders
EEW	Shaking alert based on threshold values	Audio. No visualisation in Task 3.5.	First responders Civil protection / Critical infrastructure
EEW	Map of shaking intensity	Map of macroseismic intensity (EMS-98) at three instances in time, corresponding to estimates using increasing amounts of stations. No time for displaying uncertainty or ranges on maps. Indication of uncertainty only textual.	Platform operator And First responders Civil protection / Critical infrastructure (if linked to systems to automatically switch off machinery, alert workers in dangerous locations)
EEW	Map of lead times	This information will be used for the EEW alert, but not displayed in task 3.5.	Platform operator
RRE	ShakeMap	Map of acceleration (e.g. PGA) or macroseismic intensity, including ranges of low, best and high estimates of shaking using a slider.	Business / Operators / Civic protection / First responders
OEF RRE	Targeted shaking at Points of Interest (POIs)	Graph or table of shaking estimates (e.g. PGA) for point(s) of interest indicated on the map.	Business / Operators First responders / Civic protection / Municipalities

The different phases of earthquake warning each have their own types of maps. The OEF information is displayed on hazard maps. From a technical point of view, OEF works with the increase in the seismic hazard over a specific time window: short (days), moderate (weeks) or long (months) durations. The background, normal or regular hazard is for example a national earthquake hazard map. The OEF part is the time-dependent map showing the hazard for the coming period. Classically, seismic hazard is shown as e.g. PGA for a return period of e.g. 475 years. In the TURNkey project,

however, the alternative approach has been taken: showing the probability of exceeding a chosen level of PGA for a chosen time frame, for example, the daily probability of exceeding a PGA of 0.05 g or the corresponding macroseismic intensity of V. A third type of map that is relevant for OEF is the probability gain, which is the ratio between the time-dependent hazard over the background hazard. The time-dependent hazard can be the low, best or high estimate, while the background hazard is always taken as the best estimate.

The EEW maps are produced very fast after an earthquake. Based on data from only a few stations, a first EEW map of actual shaking is produced within a few seconds from the earthquake's nucleation, provided the region is equipped with seismometers. This map is improved during the on-going earthquake as data from more stations come in. At some point, when the information on the EEW map with respect to the observed levels of shaking, magnitude and epicentre become stable and the earthquake ends, the EEW map evolves into the RRE map. This is generally after a few minutes from the earthquake's origin time. The RRE maps are more sophisticated, because models of Ground Motion Prediction Equations (GMPEs) and soil amplification are taken into account. There is no time to calculate this during the very fast production of the EEW maps.

The audio alert as a warning within EEW is not part of task 3.5. Given that people are exposed to different kinds of alerts from many devices all day long, the EEW should stand out in some way or the other. Although the lead times will probably be part of the Decision Support System on the FWCR platform, it might not be shown to the end-users. Therefore, the lead times map is not considered any further in task 3.5, apart from showing an example. The EEW maps showing shaking levels might or might not be visible to the end-user. At the time of issuing this report, no decision has been made.

Points of interest can represent certain assets for the end-users, such as hospitals, schools, bridges, railroads and chemical plants. They can be points, areas or linear features.

Who will see what information on the FWCR platform is relevant for the visualisations developed in this task. The end-users are defined here as businesses and operators, first responders and civil protection. These people generally have a non-technical background with respect to seismology. On the other hand, the platform operators and the national seismological authorities do have a technical background, but they are not the main target of the FWCR platform. The dashboard on the FWCR platform will contain maps presented as images with a limited level of interaction via a geoviewer.

5.5 Types of visualisations

5.5.1 Definition

Based on Table 5.2, there are two types of visualization products defined:

1. A **map with a slider** to include uncertainty. What is shown on the map will be based on different data:
 1. Time-dependent hazard for OEF: probability of exceedance for a given PGA value for the next time period, slider shows low-best-high estimate range.
 2. Gain in hazard for OEF: daily gain in probability of exceedance relative to the background hazard, slider shows low-best-high estimate range.
 3. Shake maps for RRE, slider shows low-best-high estimate range.
2. Estimates of shaking for **points of interest**, including the low-best-high estimate range displayed as a band or as error bars.

Easy-to-understand means that good choices need to be made for the following aspects of the maps:

1. Title of the map
2. Use of colours on the map
3. Legend text
4. Other text, such as short explanations

The title of the map should be as short as possible and still be informative. Recommendations about the use of colours are taken from Section 4.6. We have implemented 4 colour scales (monochrome reds, viridis, fire and yellow-orange-red) for PGA. The monochrome colour scale was chosen, because of simplicity, viridis is one of the colour scales from Figure 4.13, fire comes from <https://coloret.holoviz.org> and yellow-orange-red are inspired by kry from Figure 4.13. The standard EMS-98 colour scale is used for macroseismic intensity. End-users might be used to certain colour scales, such as the EMS-98 intensity colour scale or their own colour scales. In addition, displaying colours on a coloured background, e.g. a topographic map, poses a challenge. The colours of the background can interfere with the colours of the estimate of shaking. An example is shown in Figure 5.4 for the macroseismic intensity map using Google Maps as a background with a transparency of 50% for the macroseismic intensity data and cartopy (simple lines) background with no transparency for the macroseismic intensity data. The drafts included options for the background map using cartopy, Google Maps and Open Streetmaps. Another influence on how the PGA looks is if the values are plotted on a logarithmic or linear scale and with contours or graduated colours. Examples of graduated colours, contours, linear or logarithmic scales are included in Chapter 6.

Figure 5.4: Effect of background on displaying the macroseismic intensity data. Example of best estimate for Testbed 2. Top: Google Maps background with transparency. Bottom: cartopy background without transparency.

Same as the title text, the legend text should be short and informative. There needs to be a balance between what is scientifically correct and what is still understandable for the non-technical audience. All these aspects are considered in the visualisations shown in the online poll (Chapter 6) which were included in the online interactive poll to gather feedback. One example of each is described in Sections 5.5.2 to 5.5.4.

5.5.2 Examples for RRE

The examples for the RRE maps come from two Testbeds. The details of the type of data and the earthquakes are included in Table 5.3.

Table 5.3: Testbed examples for RRE maps

Testbed	Location	Earthquake	Type of data
6	Groningen, the Netherlands	M = 3.4 Zeerijp, 8 January 2018	PGA
2	Pyrenees, France	M = 4.3 Lourdes, 30 December 2012	Macroseismic intensity and PGA

The Groningen example is used for PGA (Figure 5.5) and the Lourdes example for macroseismic intensity (Figure 5.6). The figures show the position of the slider and the corresponding map for either low, best or high estimate of shaking. The end-user will see one map at the time.

Figure 5.5: RRE PGA example from Testbed 6 (Groningen, the Netherlands) showing low estimate (top), best estimate (middle) and high estimate (bottom) of shaking on a cartopy background, for contoured PGA on a linear scale.

Figure 5.6: RRE macroseismic intensity (EMS-98 colour scale) example from Testbed 2 (Pyrenees, France/Spain) showing low estimate (top), best estimate (middle) and high estimate (bottom) of shaking on a cartopy background.

5.5.3 Examples for OEF

The example for the OEF maps comes from Testbed 4 (Patras, Greece) for aftershocks following the M_w 6.8 earthquake in the Ionian Sea, near the island of Zakynthos (Greece) on 25 October 2018 at 22:54 (UTC). The epicentre of his earthquake was located about 133 km from Patras and the hypocentre was at 14 km depth. The earthquake caused serious damage to the port of Zakynthos and to a 15th century monastery on the island of Strofades. There were power outages on Zakynthos and schools were closed on 26 October 2018 (source: [Wikipedia](#)).

The OEF visualisation (Figures 5.7, 5.8 and 5.9) shows three maps at one time. The background hazard map always shows the best estimate, while the time-dependent maps have choices for low, best and high estimates. The forecast is calculated for the next 24 hours starting on 26 October 2018 00:00.

The background hazard map is shown on the left, because it is fixed. The two time-dependent maps are shown on the right. The time-dependent hazard map is showing similar data as the background hazard map, but with different values. Therefore, it is plotted in the same row (top) as the background hazard. On the hazard maps, the hazard is expressed as daily chance of exceeding a PGA of 0.05 g, corresponding to a macroseismic intensity of V (Caprio et al, 2015). The probability gain data is a different type of data, and therefore shown below the time-dependent hazard map. Because of the layout of the three panels, each OEF set is shown on one page in Figure 5.7, Figure 5.8 and Figure 5.9. for the low, best and high estimate of shaking, respectively.

TB4 Patras, Greece

Figure 5.7: OEF example for the low estimate. Top left: background or regular hazard map expressed as daily chance of exceeding PGA of 0.05 g, corresponding to a macroseismic intensity of V. Top right: time-dependent or current hazard map showing the chance of exceeding PGA of 0.05 g for the next 24 hours. Bottom right: probability gain for the next 24 hours. Note: the titles of the time-dependent maps show an arbitrary date and time.

TB4 Patras, Greece

Figure 5.8: Same as Figure 5.7, here showing the best estimate.

TB4 Patras, Greece

Figure 5.9: Same as Figure 5.7, here showing the high estimate.

5.5.4 Examples for EEW

The EEW maps are produced very fast and are almost immediately replaced by a newer version. Therefore, there cannot be too much information on it. Work Package 3 partners agreed to not add visual information about uncertainties other than text. The proposal is to qualitatively describe the three ground shaking accuracy levels by adding “Level 1: High uncertainty” to the first EEW map, “Level 2: Medium uncertainty” to the second EEW map and “Level 3: Low uncertainty” to the final EEW map. These maps (Figure 5.10) are the same as in Figure 4.6, with the extra text added.

Figure 5.10: EEW maps (same as Figure 4.6) with textual uncertainty information added.

5.5.5 Example for Points of Interest

The dashboard on the FWCR platform will show assets for the end-user. The estimates of shaking can be shown for those assets at the Points of Interest (POI). The shaking estimates at certain locations are extracted from the database, either RRE or OEF. The example for the POI is taken from the RRE estimates of shaking for Testbed 6 (Groningen, the Netherlands), for the earthquake shown in Figure 5.5. Two types of POI are defined, i.e. individual points and line features. Examples of points are hospitals, historical buildings, factories, airports, schools etc. Examples of linear features are roads and railways. The estimates of shaking at the POI are shown in Figure 5.11.

Figure 5.11: Estimates of shaking at POIs. Left: RRE shake map (PGA) of best estimate with numbered POI and one example linear POI. Top right: at a linear feature, in this case a railway. The best estimate is shown as the solid green line, the range between low and high estimate is shown as a coloured band around the best estimate. Bottom right: estimates of shaking at the POI, numbers correspond to numbers on the map. The best estimate is shown by the symbol and the range between low to high estimate is shown as an error bar.

6 TURNKEY PARTNER CONSULTATION

An online interactive poll was organised to gather feedback on drafts of the products on 6 May 2021. The application used for the online poll was Mentimeter. The visualisations were presented to the participants. Questions were asked about different aspects, such as the understandability of titles, different options for colour scales, linear or logarithmic representation of the data and the slider for low, best or high estimates of shaking. The first question for each section was in the form of a vote for a certain option. Most voting questions had 18-20 respondents. This voting question was always followed by a free-field question where participants could type any comments they wanted. This second feature allowed people who would normally not speak up in a large group to give their feedback. Using the open questions also ensured that all comments were saved for later analysis.

“Thanks for this meeting, that was really a fantastic way to conduct it – giving everybody the opportunity to express their opinion without lengthy discussions. This was the most fun meeting I had in a long time!”

Quote from one of the participants

A news item about this session was posted on the TURNkey website:

<https://earthquake-turnkey.eu/gathering-feedback-about-easy-to-understand-estimates-of-ground-shaking-during-interactive-online-poll-session-on-6-may-2021/>

The results are presented in the next sections, following the setup of the poll: first RRE with POI (Section 6.1), next OEF (Section 6.2) and last EEW (Section 6.3). Each section shows the graphical representation of poll results (without captions) and summarises the most important entries for the open question in the recommendations. The poll results are automatically produced by Mentimeter in a standard format. The font size tends to be quite small to read. The histograms showing the results about the understandability display from left to right entries for 0 (not understandable at all) to 5 (perfect). The recommendations are included in the next version of the easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking, which are described in Deliverable D3.13 for further implementation in the FCWR platform.

6.1 Results for RRE and POI

Examples of RRE maps are shown in Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6 and estimates at POI in Figure 5.11.

Understandability of map title

Mentimeter

18

Recommendations for map title (Figure 5.5): not mention Testbed, write out acronyms, first date written out (e.g. 8 January 2018) and specify time of earthquake.

Understandability of colour scale text

Mentimeter

18

Recommendations for colour scale text (Figure 5.5): write out acronyms, use SI units (m/s^2 instead of % of g).

Options for the design of the slider are shown below, followed by the question about preference for a design.

a)

b)

c)

Preference for slider design

Mentimeter

Recommendations for slider options: equal preference for slider or buttons. If using buttons, then use a different colour. Suggestion for asking end-users for preference. Low-best-high is a good choice of words, but it needs to be explained, e.g. by an information icon with a window pop-up.

Four options for colour scales were presented below, followed by the question about preference for a colour scale. Viridis is one of the scientific colour scales described in section 4.5.

Colour scale preference

Mentimeter

Colour scale: should end user have a choice?

Mentimeter

Recommendations for colour scale: preference for either fire or reds. Suggestion for asking end-users for preference and if they want to have a choice.

During the earlier Work Package 3 discussions it was suggested that all results should be shown on a scale with a fixed maximum, either Testbed-specific or for Europe. Examples of (arbitrary) maximums are shown below for Testbed (top, 30 % of g) or European (bottom, 200% of g) on the next page, compare with Figure 5.5. The need for testbed-specific or European maximum seems to be confirmed during the poll.

M=3.4, TB6 Zeerijp (the Netherlands) earthquake, 2018-01-08
Best estimate of shaking (PGA)

M=3.4, TB6 Zeerijp (the Netherlands) earthquake, 2018-01-08
Best estimate of shaking (PGA)

Option needed for maximum of colour scale

Mentimeter

20

Recommendation for maximum of colour scale: implement option to specify maximum of colour scale.

Following the poll, all Testbed coordinators were asked in a separate email to provide minimum and maximum values for PGA and macroseismic intensity for their Testbeds. The Testbed-specific values are summarised in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Testbed-specific minimum and maximum values for estimates of shaking

Testbed	Location	Minimum PGA (m/s ²)	Maximum PGA (m/s ²)	Minimum EMS-98 intensity	Maximum EMS-98 intensity
TB1	Bucharest	0.01	3.0	II	X
TB2	Pyrenees	0.03	2.8	II	VIII
TB3	Iceland	0.01	13.0	II	VIII
TB4	Patras and Aegio	-	2.4	-	VIII
TB5	Maritime ports on Gioia Tauro	0.03	5.9	III	IX-X
TB6	Groningen	0.01	3.0	II	VIII
TB7	World	-	19.6	II	XII
TB8	Mobile (Europe)	0.03	9.4	III	XII

For the RRE macroseismic intensity maps, different options for the colour scale and legend were presented below, followed by the question about preference.

Preference for intensity scale option

Mentimeter

20

Recommendations for intensity scale: use roman numbers with the EMS-98 text.

General layout for linear features and points of interest

Mentimeter

Recommendations for POIs: write out acronyms, use SI units (m/s^2 instead of % of g). There might be a need for different threshold levels (ask end-users). Include A-B for linear features on the map and on the graph for the direction. More panels are required if there are more than one linear feature.

6.2 Results for OEF

Examples of OEF maps are shown in Figure 5.7, Figure 5.8 and Figure 5.9.

Layout of 3 maps

Mentimeter

Recommendations for OEF layout: none.

Understandability of title of background hazard map

Mentimeter

Recommendations for background hazard map: consider “normal” or “regular” instead of “background”.

Colour scale text of background hazard map

Mentimeter

Recommendations for colour scale text for background hazard: do not use green as a colour, because more intense green might suggest safer while it is the opposite. Consider alternative words.

Understandability of title of time-dependent hazard map

Mentimeter

Recommendations for title of time-dependent hazard map: suggestions for improved title “Daily chance of experiencing strong shaking - 24h forecast starting from 6 May 2021 13:00” (which is time of issuing the map)”. Suggestion to ask end-users if they prefer chance, probability or likelihood.

Understandability of title of change in hazard map

Mentimeter

19

Recommendations for title of probability gain map: suggestion for improved title “Increase in daily chance of experiencing strong shaking in 24h starting 6 May 13:00”.

Colour scale text of change in hazard map

Mentimeter

18

Recommendations for colour scale text of probability gain map: add an information icon explaining what “probability gain” is. Suggestion to ask end-users if they prefer chance, probability or likelihood. Use the preference consistently on the 3 maps.

Need for information icon

Mentimeter

20

Recommendation for information icons: include them next to titles and colour bars, in a consistent way.

Perception of the information is influenced by plotting on a linear or logarithmic scale and as graduated or contoured colours. The four combined options were presented on the next page, followed by the question about preference for one of the options.

a) Lin & contours

c) Log & contours

b) Lin & graduated

d) Log & graduated

e) No preference

Preference for lin/log contours/graduated colours for OEF

■ Mentimeter

18

Recommendations for lin/log and contours/graduated colours: discussion after the poll with OEF specialists resulted in a choice for contours and linear scale for hazard maps and logarithmic scale for the probability gain.

Option needed for maximum of colour scale for OEF

Mentimeter

17

Recommendations for a maximum for the OEF maps: discussion after the poll with OEF specialists indicated that no testbed-specific maximum values are needed for OEF maps.

Do you also want POIs in the OEF maps?

Mentimeter

16

Recommendations for POIs on OEF maps: these need to be implemented on OEF maps.

6.3 Results for EEW

Add uncertainty information as text?

Mentimeter

18

Recommendations for uncertainty on EEW maps: only as text, but remove "level 1", "level 2" and "level 3". Only keep "high uncertainty", "medium uncertainty" and "high uncertainty".

Do you also want POIs in the EEW maps?

Mentimeter

18

Recommendations for POIs on EEW maps: there is a wish, but there might not be time to digest the information. In addition, the EEW maps might not be shown but only form input for the DSS.

7 END-USER CONSULTATION: EXTRA ACTION

A final end-user consultation round is planned by WP2 to be executed with the first operational FWCR platform. This final round is planned for the end of 2021. This is too late to be included in this report. Based on the results of the Work Package 3 poll (Chapter 6), however, the top 7 questions for the end-users were selected for a short questionnaire by email. The questionnaire was carried out by Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation and Nutcracker Research Ltd.. The questionnaire was sent out in July 2021. Responses received up until 20 August are included in the analysis.

The short questionnaire consisted of 8 questions using the visualisations of the updated images after the Work Package 3 poll. The questionnaire was sent out in English to business and critical infrastructure end-users from France, Iceland and the Netherlands (Testbeds 2, 3 and 6). The questionnaire was translated into local languages (Romanian, Greek and Italian) for the end-users from civil protection and first responders (Testbeds 1, 4 and 5). Nineteen responses were received.

The results of the end-user consultation are visualised similarly to the Mentimeter results in Chapter 6). First, a screenshot of the question (English version) is presented, then the graphical representation of questionnaire results is given and next the recommendations for implementation in the FCWR platform. The first question was what organisation the end-user works for. The other questions were about the visualisations.

2

On a daily basis, the TURNkey platform will be able to generate an estimate of the probability of strong shaking in the next 24 hours. This is not a prediction with 100% certainty but rather a probabilistic forecast. For instance, you will be able to compare a map showing the regular probability for an average day with another showing an increase in probability of an earthquake or aftershock happening in the next 24 hours.

Please select the best and second-best titles for these maps:

Operational Earthquake Forecasting following the magnitude 6.8 Ionean Sea earthquake on 25 October 2018 at 22:54 (UTC)

- 24h forecast** for strong shaking from 9 June 2021 13:00
- Current daily forecast** for strong shaking from 9 June 2021 13:00
- Current daily chance** of strong shaking until 10 June 2021 13:00
- Current daily probability** of strong shaking until 10 June 2021 13:00
- Current daily likelihood** of strong shaking until 10 June 2021 13:00

N.B. Only the English version with 4 respondents had the top option with “24h”. Therefore, only the results from the translated versions to the first responders and civil protection (15 respondents) were analysed here.

Conclusion: there is a preference for “probability” (first choice) and “likelihood” (second choice).

Recommendation for title of OEF maps: “probability” (or the translated equivalent) is the best choice to be used in the title of OEF maps.

3

After an earthquake has occurred, the platform will show you the level of estimated shaking experienced in the region. You will see three maps with three estimates of ground shaking which will be labelled 'low', 'best' and 'high' estimates. The three levels of estimates are based on the level of uncertainty in the data. More uncertainty in the data is expressed by a larger value for the standard deviations included. This will go up to two standard deviations above or below the mean. This accounts for the high and low estimates. The estimate with the lowest level of uncertainty is the one labelled 'best'.

These maps show an example of low, best and high estimates of shaking from an earthquake that happened in the Pyrenees on 20 December 2012. The colours indicate the intensity of the earthquake.

Not at all helpful Not very helpful Slightly helpful Somewhat helpful Helpful Very helpful Extremely helpful

How useful is having the best estimate

How useful is having all three estimates?

Conclusion: it is very to extremely helpful for the end-users to have the best estimate of shaking and also the uncertainty range.

Recommendation for the estimate with uncertainty: give this a prominent place on the platform

4

Would you prefer to be able to switch from seeing the low, best or high estimates by moving a slider (left) or clicking a button (right)?

- Moving a slider (left)
- Clicking a button (right)

Conclusion: the end-users have a slight preference for the slider, similar to what was expressed by the Work Package 3 partners. However, the preference is not strong.

Recommendation for slider design: it is up to Beta80 to implement either a slider or a button, whatever fits best in the overall design of the platform.

5

After an earthquake has happened, TURNkey will show you a map showing peak ground acceleration or macro seismic intensity. Using the arrows on the right, please order the following colour options going from your most preferred to your least preferred.

Option 1

Option 2

Option 3

Option 4

My own colour scheme

Conclusion: the scientific colour scale viridis is not popular among the end-users. Their preference is for fire or the less bright yellow-orange-red. There is no wish to be able to select a user-defined colour scale.

Recommendation for colour scales: implement colour scale “fire” for RRE maps.

6

There is an option to toggle in the colour settings between maximum value for the region and maximum value for an earthquake. Using the maximum for earthquakes, all earthquakes would show up with equally intense colours, also the small ones. So it might look severe while it is only minor. Using the maximum for the region, a small earthquake would have pale colours and a strong earthquake more intense colours.

Would you like to be able to adjust the maximum value of the colour scale as shown?

- Yes
- No
- Makes no difference
- Unclear

Conclusion: there is a strong wish to be able to adjust the maximum of the colour scale to either the expected maximum of the region or the maximum of the earthquake shown in the platform.

Recommendation for maximum of colour scale: implement two options for the maximum of the colour scale in the user settings, either defined by region or defined by dataset.

7

TURNkey will allow end-users to identify specific points of interest for them (e.g. the location of critical built assets). TURNkey will then show the level of shaking at each point of interest on two graphs. The error bars and the shaded band show the range from low to high estimates of shaking. The dashed red line shows a threshold level which could be set to a standard level or to a level that relates to the construction quality of the point of interest.

Would you like to be able to define your own threshold levels for your points of interest?

- Yes
- No
- Makes no difference
- Unclear

Conclusion: there is a strong wish to be able to include end-user's thresholds.

Recommendation for thresholds at POIs: allow the definition of end-user thresholds in user settings.

8 CONCLUSIONS

For the development of easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking the results from the first end-user consultation round are important. The end-users could understand a maximum of five warning levels and need a simple vocabulary to describe warning levels. In addition, precise numbers to refer to the impact or the likelihood are to be avoided, but easier to understand general terms should be used.

Various existing solutions for maps corresponding to the OEF, EEW and RRE phases have served as inspiration for our easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking. Only one of the existing examples showed uncertainty, but in a difficult to understand way.

The basic design for the easy-to-understand estimates of ground shaking consists of a map with a slider. The phase defines the type of information on the map, e.g. shake map for RRE and hazard for OEF. The slider defines the level of the estimate, being either the best estimate based on the mean or median values at each coordinate or the low or high estimate based on the mean minus or plus two standard deviations. In addition to the maps, two graphs were presented for shaking estimates at points of interest. The first graph shows the mean peak ground acceleration along a linear feature such as a railway track. The range from low to high estimate is shown as a shaded band. The second graph shows the estimate at a point, such as a hospital or bridge, with the low to high estimates around the mean indicated by an error bar.

The basic designs were proof-tested by project members of the Work Package 3 during an interactive online poll session. Aspects that were tested were the concept of the slider, colour scales, legend and title texts, linear or logarithmic scales and graduated or contoured colours. The outcomes were used to improve the easy-to-understand visualisations.

As an extra, a short questionnaire with 7 key questions was circulated among the end-users by Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation and Nutcracker Research Ltd. The outcomes indicate that the end-users regard the best estimate and the range as helpful information. They understand “probability” (and translated equivalents) the best in the titles for OEF maps. They have expressed a preference for the “fire” colour scale for RRE maps, for the ability to adjust the maximum of the colour scale and the addition of their own threshold values. Similar to the Work Package 3 partners, there is no strong preference for a slider or buttons for the selection of estimates of shaking levels. These useful additional results are included into the requirements document for the implementation on the platform (D3.13).

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